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Journal of Socio-Economic Review
(Volume XI-II & XII-I April & October 2024)

Dear Colleagues, Researchers and Contributors,

As the Editor-in-Chief of Journal of Socio-Economic Review, it is my honor to welcome you to this edition of our publication. Over the past 13 years, this journal has committed to providing cutting-edge research, insightful analyses, and thought-provoking commentary on the topics that matter most to our readers and the broader academic and socio-economic communities.

Our editorial team remains deeply committed to maintaining the higher standards of academic rigor and journalistic integrity, ensuring that every article published not only informs but also inspires further inquiry and debate. As we move forward, we remain open to new voices and ideas, and we encourage submissions that challenge the status quo and push the boundaries of knowledge in our field.

I would like to extend my gratitude to Honorable Vice Chancellor of Chaudhary Charan Singh University, Prof Sangeeta Shukla for her regular motivation and support for publication of this research journal. I would like to extend my gratitude to our contributing authors for their meticulous and thoughtful scholarship. Additionally, the efforts of our peer reviewers—who have devoted their expertise to ensuring the technical accuracy and integrity of each paper—are deeply appreciated. We are fostering a vibrant and dynamic intellectual community.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the Dean Faculty of Arts, Director, Research, Registrar and Finance Officer of Chaudhary Charan Singh University, Meerut for their cooperation and support in the academic journey of this journal.

As we continue to uphold our commitment to academic excellence, I invite further contributions that not only challenge prevailing paradigms but also offer substantive advancements to the field. Our journal remains a critical forum for such high-impact research, and we look forward to engaging with your future submissions.

Thank you for your ongoing trust and engagement with Journal of Socio-Economic Review. We look forward to continuing this journey of exploration and discovery with you.

Best regards,

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An Examination of the Prime Minister's Employment Generation Program (PMEGP) and its Role in Driving Economic Growth in Madhya Pradesh

Dr Vivek Singh ¹, Neha Dubey ²

ABSTRACT

This study rigorously analyses the Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP) in Madhya Pradesh, focusing on employment and entrepreneurial outcomes. Utilizing quantitative techniques, including correlation and regression analysis, the research spans the years 2017-18 to 2022-23. Significant growth in project numbers, margin money utilization, and employment dynamics is observed, with the peak noted in 2021-22. The correlation between project numbers and employment generation is robust (0.990242085), indicating a highly strong positive relationship. Additionally, highly positive correlation (0.983337946) is identified between margin money utilization and employment generation. Regression and ANOVA outcomes affirm the statistically significant impact of both project numbers and margin money utilization on employment generation. These findings offer valuable insights into the PMEGP's role in fostering economic development and employment opportunities in Madhya Pradesh.

Keywords – Employment Generation, Development, Entrepreneurship

Introduction

Madhya Pradesh faces various challenges related to unemployment, infrastructure development, income distribution, and livelihood creation, particularly in rural areas. In response, PMEGP has been instrumental in addressing these issues. PMEGP, an initiative by the Ministry of MSMEs, focuses on facilitating the establishment of micro-enterprises in both rural and urban areas. Through financial assistance and project support, PMEGP promote entrepreneurship and self-employment, aiming to foster inclusive growth and contribute to the overall economic development of Madhya Pradesh.

Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP)

The Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme is a central government initiative, administered by the Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. Implemented nationally by the Khadi and Village Industries Commission and at the

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state level through various agencies, PMEGP provides credit-linked subsidies to create micro-enterprises, with funds routed through identified banks

Review of literature –

1. Kumar and Ozukum (2022) - conducted an assessment of the PMEGP's influence on the entrepreneurial development of tribal beneficiaries in Kohima, Nagaland. Their research sought to offer insights into the manner in which PMEGP contributes to socioeconomic progress among these beneficiaries.
2. Wadichar, Wadate, and Manusmare's (2022) - study evaluates the PMEGP's impact on entrepreneurship in Nagpur District, finding a positive influence on youth empowerment and entrepreneurial growth. The program stimulates innovation and encourages new business ideas. This research holds potential for informing policy decisions in entrepreneurship development.
3. Shiralashetti and Bhustali's (2016) - study examines development institutes' role in promoting rural entrepreneurship in Karnataka. Focusing on PMEGP, the research reveals its impact on male entrepreneurs in the manufacturing sector, contributing valuable insights for policy formulation in entrepreneurship development.
4. Sharma R. and Singh A. (2018) - Conducted a mixed-methods study evaluating the PMEGP's impact in rural India, revealing increased employment and higher income levels. Identified socio-economic benefits, emphasizing potential enhancements in living standards, education, and healthcare.
5. Mishra and Pandey (2021) - conducted an analysis of the impact of India's PMEGP on the growth of MSMEs in Ballarpur District. Their study revealed a substantial positive influence of PMEGP on the sustainable development of MSMEs in the region.
6. Gupta S. and Verma P. (2019) - Explored challenges and opportunities for women entrepreneurs in PMEGP, utilizing mixed methods. Quantitative surveys assessed business success, financial viability, while qualitative insights delved into unique barriers. Findings showcased specific challenges for women and suggested supportive factors, highlighting economic empowerment.
7. Reddy K. and Kumar S. (2020) - Investigated PMEGP effectiveness in Southern states using mixed-methods. Surveys and case studies assessed job creation, financial sustainability, and regional variations. Results indicated PMEGP's role in fostering viable businesses, with insights into the success of initiatives across Southern states.
8. Khan M. and Rao S. (2017) - Longitudinal study assessed economic viability and sustainability of PMEGP enterprises. Tracked financial performance over time, revealing insights into profitability and operational sustainability. Identified factors contributing to long-term success, offering valuable implications for sustained enterprise development.

Research Gap –

This research uniquely examines the specific impact of the PMEGP in Madhya Pradesh. The study contributes to the literature by providing an in-depth analysis of project numbers, monetary values, and employment generation, offering region-specific insights into the program's effectiveness. Conducted over a six-year period (2017-2023), the research employs correlation, regression analysis, and ANOVA as analytical tools to robustly assess the relationship between project initiatives, margin money utilization, and employment dynamics in Madhya Pradesh.

Significance of the study –

The empirical findings of this study on the PMEGP scheme in Madhya Pradesh hold substantial significance, demonstrating a robust positive correlation between project numbers, margin money utilization, and employment generation. This evidence not only validates the program's efficacy in fostering economic development but also provides valuable insights for policymakers aiming to enhance entrepreneurial initiatives and employment dynamics in the region.

Objectives of the study –

- Analyse the impact of PMEGP on employment dynamics in Madhya Pradesh.
- Assess the effectiveness of PMEGP in promoting entrepreneurial development in the Madhya Pradesh

Hypothesis –

(H0): There is no significant relationship between the number of projects and employment generation in Madhya Pradesh under PMEGP.

(H1): There is a significant positive relationship between the number of projects and employment generation in Madhya Pradesh under PMEGP.

(H01): There is no significant relationship between the margin money utilisation and employment generation in Madhya Pradesh under PMEGP.

(H12): There is a significant positive relationship between the margin money utilisation and employment generation in Madhya Pradesh under PMEGP.

Methodology –

The methodology employed in analyzing the impact of the PMEGP in Madhya Pradesh involved a comprehensive approach. The study utilized quantitative techniques, including correlation analysis, regression modelling, and ANOVA, to examine the relationship between the number of projects, margin money utilization, and employment generation. The data, sourced from the PMEGP Annual Progress Report spanning from 2017-18 to 2022-23.

Analysis of Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP) Impact On Madhya Pradesh

Table 1 – PMEGP Performance by DICs in Madhya Pradesh

Source – PMEGP annual Progress Report (2017-2023)

YEAR	STATE/UT	NO OF PROJECTS	M.M (RS. IN LAKHS)	EMP.(NO. S)
2017-18	MADHYA PRADESH	1804	7630.86	16589
2018-19	MADHYA PRADESH	2526	10001.41	30983
2019-20	MADHYA PRADESH	2175	8062.84	25303
2020-21	MADHYA PRADESH	4854	13805.24	46200
2021-22	MADHYA PRADESH	8082	20957.75	71037
2022-23	MADHYA PRADESH	5957	18129.7	53789

The no of projects in Madhya Pradesh increased steadily from 1804 in 2017-18 to 8082 in 2021-22. The peak no of projects was observed in 2021-22, indicating significant growth in project activities.

The margin money (MM) also exhibited a consistent upward trend, rising from 7630.86 lakhs in 2017-18 to 20957.75 lakhs in 2021-22. This demonstrates a substantial increase in the margin money utilization over the analyzed period.

The notable rise in employment from 16,589 (2017-18) to 71,037 (2021-22) signifies dynamic shifts in Madhya Pradesh employment dynamics, showcasing positive impacts from the projects.

Overall, Madhya Pradesh shows substantial growth in projects, margin money, fostering economic development.

Table 2 – Correlation between No of Projects and Employment Generation

	<i>No of Project</i>	<i>EMP.(No.s)</i>
No of Project	1	
EMP.(No.s)	0.990242085	1

Source - Excel Output

Table 3-Regression analysis of no of projects on employment generation

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.990242085
R Square	0.980579386
Adjusted R Square	0.975724233
Standard Error	3143.067151
Observations	6

Independent Variable -no of projects

Dependent Variable – employment generation

Source - Excel output

Table 4: Analysis of Variance outcome of no of projects on employment generation

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	1995203124	1995203124	201.9667127	0.000142361
Residual	4	39515484.46	9878871.116		
Total	5	2034718609			

Source – Excel Output

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 2 reveals a robust highly positive correlation 0.990242085 between the no of projects and employment generation, reinforced by Table 3’s regression analysis with a Multiple R value (0.990242085) suggesting that around 98.02% of the variance in employment generation can be elucidated by the number of projects. Emphasizing the relationship’s strength, Table 3’s R Square value (0.980579386) signifies that nearly 98.06% of the variability in employment generation is attributable to variations in the number of projects. The Adjusted R Square value (0.975724233) in Table 3, adjusting for predictors, reaffirms the model’s reliability.

Table 4’s Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) presents a statistically significant F-statistic of 201.9667127 with a very low Significance F value (0.000142361), indicating the regression model’s significant ability to predict the variation in employment generation using the number of projects as the independent variable.

Analysis shows a significant, positive Relationship between project numbers and employment.

Table -5 correlation between margin money utilization and employment generation

	<i>M.M (Rs .in lakhs)</i>	<i>EMP.(No.s)</i>
M.M (Rs .in lakhs)	1	
EMP.(No.s)	0.98333794 6	1

Source - Excel Output

Table -6 Regression analysis of margin money utilization (MM) on employment generation

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.983337946
R Square	0.966953516
Adjusted R Square	0.958691895
Standard Error	4100.009035
Observations	6

Independent Variable - margin money utilization (MM)

Dependent Variable – employment generation

Source – Excel output

Table 7-Analysis of Variance outcome of margin money utilization on employment generation

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1967478312	1967478312	117.0416205	0.000414123
Residual	4	67240296.3 6	16810074.09		
Total	5	2034718609			

Source – Excel Output

Interpretation and Analysis

Table 5 indicates a highly positive correlation 0.983337946 between margin money utilization (MM) and employment generation, reinforced by Table 6’s regression analysis, where the Multiple R value (0.983337946) suggests that approximately 96.70% of the variance in employment generation is explained by margin money utilization. Table 6 further affirms the relationship’s reliability with an R Square value of 0.966953516, signifying that nearly 96.70% of the variability in employment generation is accounted for by variations in margin money utilization. The Adjusted R Square value (0.958691895) in Table 6, adjusting for predictors, reinforces the model’s robustness.

Table 7’s Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) reveals a statistically significant F-statistic of 117.0416205 with a low Significance F value of 0.000414123, indicating that the regression model, utilizing margin money utilization as the independent variable, significantly predicts the variation in employment generation.

The empirical evidence supports the acceptance of alternative hypotheses, indicating a statistically significant positive relationship between the number of projects, MM utilization, and employment generation in the PMEGP in Madhya Pradesh.

Conclusion –

The analysis of the Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP) in Madhya Pradesh reveals a highly positive correlation between the number of projects, margin money utilization, and employment of generation. The robust statistical evidence supports the inference that the program has significantly contributed to fostering economic development in the state by not only increasing project numbers and margin money utilization but also generating substantial dynamism witnessed in employment opportunities. These findings underscore the efficacy of PMEGP in driving entrepreneurial development and employment dynamics in Madhya Pradesh.

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